

TESTING A SYSTEM FOR DOPPLER SOUNDING OF AGW/TID FOR DEPLOYMENT NEAR ANTARCTIC PENINSULA

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Doppler HF radio sounding is used for the long time to measure the characteristics of ionospheric plasma irregularities and more recently also to study travelling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs). The method of Doppler diagnostics of the ionosphere was developed in several fields. A method of frequency and angular sounding of the ionosphere was developed at the Institute of Radio Astronomy of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IRA NASU) and further extended to studying TIDs. Another promising variant, the continuous multi-point Doppler HF sounding on quasi-vertical radio paths suitable for monitoring of TIDs was developed at the Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences (IAP CAS) and then launched into operation in several regions of the Globe.

Near Antarctic Peninsula is a world's strongest hotspot of atmospheric gravity waves (AGW) which manifest themselves as TIDs at the ionospheric heights. Therefore, organization and conducting the long-term continuous measurements in this region can make a valuable contribution to better understanding the physics of atmosphere as whole, and AGW/TIDs in particular.

Currently, we are making the plans for joint measurements in Antarctica according to the schemes similar to those developed in IAP CAS and IRA NASU. The first step in testing the options for diagnosing TIDs on both vertical and short oblique radio paths was made at the end of 2024. We have adjusted one of the Doppler HF receivers operating at the LOFAR PL610 observatory in Borowiec (Poland) to record the frequencies of monochromatic signals emitted in the vicinity of Prague. It is shown that the main details of the quasi-periodic variations of Doppler frequency shift caused by TIDs are similar on both quasi-vertical and oblique radio paths. It most likely means that the TIDs parameters can be resolved also from the signals reflected on oblique paths at distances between transmitters and receiver up to (at least) 300 km. Moreover, synchronous vertical and oblique Doppler sounding could be used to estimate more accurately the characteristics (wavelength, speed and direction of motion) of large-scale TIDs.